

TO THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION QUALITY ASSURANCE RECRUITMENT OF PERSONNEL

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Annotation. *In this article, the works carried out in the educational process, attention to the quality of education, works carried out as education, the opinions and works of scientists about the quality of education, the improvement of the quality of education information about.*

Key words: *quality of education, educational system, modern technologies, knowledge, skills or acquisition of information and rules.*

Quality is a vague term that needs to be understood by different audiences in the education system. Parents of students associate it with the development of individuality, further educational success of their children. For teachers, quality means the existence of a high-quality curriculum, the provision of educational and teaching manuals, normal working conditions; students often associate quality with the climate in the school, "comfort" in the school. Future employers (business, industry) associate the quality of education with an active life position, knowledge, skills and abilities of graduates, enabling them to make optimal decisions, etc.

Therefore, it is not surprising that some authors understand the quality of education as "the level of satisfaction of the various participants of the educational process with the services provided by the educational institution", while others understand the level of achievement of goals. "tasks".[1]

However, despite the wide discussion of the quality of education of students, the practice of ensuring the quality of education of schoolchildren still does not give the desired result in many cases.

"The change of educational paradigm led to the change of educational goals. It is aimed at a different result, a different quality. Among the majority of teachers, the idea of the quality of education has remained the same". [2]

The study of scientific literature, school practice, the experience of cooperation with school leaders, vice-principals and teachers are the goals announced to us and only the formation of personal instrumental components of the educational activity of schoolchildren. allows to determine the conflict between the traditional system.

The most important meaning of education is the self-discovery of the student, the recognition of his true personality, the creation of his image in the interaction between the teacher and the student. This is quite different from the task of imitating a model. Acquiring knowledge, skills or information and rules cannot be an end in itself. These are necessary, but not sufficient, conditions for the formation of a person, self-realization, because the destination of education in modern society is not its social functions and methods of their use, but the whole person.[3]

The purpose of the school is not knowledge itself, but the student who values this knowledge, his intelligence and spiritual development. That is, quality education is such education, the result of which is the development of the student's intellect, independent and responsible thinking, speech and work skills. Quality education is the training of personal characteristics. "At the same time, Golubeva L.M. states that "the educational process at school is still mainly focused on the transmission of information, which does not implement the main principle of humanizing education - addressing the individual, creating conditions for the full disclosure and development

of his potential. O "the entire arsenal of the teacher is aimed at increasing the level of education and does not provide activity, cognitive activity, development of students, their intellectual abilities and personality in general. The example of educational programs is indicative of this point of view. It is a means of managing and coordinating the activities of teachers in teaching: they become bureaucratic instructions and recommendations, the implementation of which can be checked ("did the teacher finish his program, did the students master the concepts and knowledge?"). »[4]

Evaluating the quality of education at school is one of the most complex pedagogical problems. Today, the forms and methods used to evaluate the quality of students' education do not allow comprehensive and completely objective evaluation, because it is not easy to determine everything that needs to be evaluated. The number of "excellent students" and "good students" in a school says little about the quality of each student's individual education, and nothing about the student's problems.

As A. Talikh noted, "today, as before, when it is not enough to reduce the quality of education to the usual percentages of academic results and other official indicators, conscious management of the school is only complete, fast and reliable information about the results of the activity of all subjects of the educational process, the level and nature of the influence of objective environmental factors".

In this regard, it seems important to create a system for analyzing the activities of the team of pedagogues for managing the quality of education in secondary schools.[7]

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